

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL SCIENCE CURRICULUM ON TWO-YEAR B. ED TRAINING IN KARNATAKA UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This paper also discusses the current state of social science pedagogy as an important stage in B.Ed. education. The main objective of this paper is to identify the objectives of social science pedagogy set by Karnataka University and to synthesize the extent to which the objectives of social science teaching have been fulfilled by the curriculum set by Karnataka University. A relevant standardized instrument has been prepared to test these objectives. A questionnaire was distributed to 56 randomly selected samples. The data was analyzed with the help of statistics. This research revealed that there is a need to change the content of social science.

Keywords: *Social Science, Syllabus*

Introduction

The present National Social Science Curriculum addresses several attempts to create a National Social Science Curriculum. Since the subjects that comprise social sciences in India are considered inadequate for employment, further changes are needed. They perceive the need to first discuss the existing perceptions of social sciences in the community and then incorporate these into the proposed content framework. To ensure that the content recommendations are adequately translated into textbooks, the NATIONAL FOCUS GROUP has also highlighted the main issues that need to be addressed to make social sciences a professionally and intellectually valuable subject of study. Social sciences cover various sub-branches of society; hence, it is important for students to develop a critical understanding of society. Selecting and organizing content in the social sciences subject is a difficult task. The potential for adding new dimensions and concerns is immense, especially in view of the student's own life experiences. It is important to restore the importance of social sciences by pointing out its indispensability in laying the foundation for a creative and analytical mindset. But it is essential to recognize that social sciences, like natural and physical sciences, engage themselves in

scientific inquiry, and to clarify how the methods applied by social sciences are different from but in no way inferior to those of natural and physical sciences.

Social sciences have a normative responsibility to create and expand a popular base for human values, trust, mutual respect, i.e. freedom, respect for diversity, etc. Thus, social science teaching should basically aim to invest moral and psychological strength in the child, so that the child can be equipped with the capacity to deal with these values, presupposing a comprehensive curriculum in which learners and teachers and children participate in the production of knowledge. The disciplines that make up social sciences, such as geography, history, political science and economics, have different approaches that often justify the preservation of boundaries.

In terms of teaching methods, pedagogy and resources, social science teaching needs to be revitalized in a way that helps learners acquire skills and knowledge in an interactive environment. The teaching of social sciences should adopt methods that promote aesthetics, creativity and critical perspectives and enable children to draw connections between the past and the present, to understand the changes taking place in society. Dramatization, problem solving and role-playing are some of the hitherto unexplored techniques that can be used.

Teaching should make greater use of resources of audio-visual materials including charts and maps, photographs and replicas of archaeological and material cultures. There is a need to shift from mere information giving to discussion and debate to make the learning process practical and participatory. The subject matter should be clarified for students through the practical experiences of individuals. It has been widely observed that cultural, social differences in classroom situations produce their own biases, and attitudes. Therefore, the teaching method should be open or unregulated. Teachers should discuss various aspects of social reality in the classroom and work towards instilling greater self-awareness in themselves and in their students.

OBJECTIVES OF TEACHING SOCIAL SCIENCES AT SECONDARY LEVEL (NCF, 2005)

The objectives of teaching Social Sciences at the secondary level of education are to develop analytical and conceptual skills that will enable learners to;

- (1) understand the processes of economic and social change and development in modern and contemporary India,
- (2) critically examine social and economic problems and challenges such as poverty, child labor, illiteracy in its various dimensions,
- (3) understand the rights and responsibilities of citizens in a democratic and secular society,
- (4) understand the roles and responsibilities of the state in the discharge of its constitutional obligations,
- (5) understand the processes of change and development in India in relation to the use of resources and the need for environmental protection, the world economy and politics, as well as appreciate the rights of local communities in their surroundings.

THE RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

According to the National Curriculum Framework-2005, education programmes train teachers to adapt to a system where education is considered as a transmission of information. There is less freedom to engage in innovative educational experiments. Experiences in the practice of a teacher-education programme are considered to be ‘given’ knowledge. Subsequently, in 2014, the NCTE brought out a content framework for the two-year B.Ed. course and provided some indicative guidelines for curriculum design in the light of the new norms and standards of 2014. As a result, Karnataka University prepared a two-year B.Ed. course. This paper aims to critically analyse and define the fundamental issues involved in the teaching of Social Science in the two-year B.Ed. subject prepared by Karnataka University, Dharwad district.

STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

“A STUDY OF SOCIAL SCIENCE TEACHING IN TWO-YEAR B.ED. EDUCATION IN KARNATAKA UNIVERSITY”

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- (i) Study of the objectives of teaching the Social Science subject prepared by Karnataka University

(ii) Explain the effective teaching of the Social Science subject prepared by Karnataka University.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the study

The current study falls under the category of qualitative research. In this study, the researchers used a descriptive survey method.

Sampling

This research was conducted on B.Ed. students and teacher educators (2nd year) of private and government colleges affiliated to Karnataka University. In this study, the researchers randomly selected 38 students (6 from each college) and 18 teacher educators (2 from each college) (four private and one government) B.Ed. students and teacher educators studying in this study were selected, namely;

- (1) Karnataka University B.Ed. College Dharwad (Government)
- (2) J.S.S. Sri Manjunatheshwar College of Education Dharwad (Private)
- (3) Shri Sai B.Ed. College, Hubli (Private)
4. Rural B.Ed. College Dharwad (Private)
5. Siddharameshwar College of Education, Dharwad (Private)

Table 1: Distribution of the Sample

S. N	Categories	Male	Female	Private College	Govt. College	Total
1	Student-Teachers	09	27	19	19	38
2	Teacher Educators	03	13	9	9	18
Grand Total		12	40	28	28	56

Figure 1: Distribution of the Sample

TOOL OF THE STUDY

The instrument 'Evaluation Scale for Social Science Subjects Related to Pedagogy and Teaching' was developed and validated by the researchers themselves. It is an open-ended questionnaire. The instruments were validated by construct validity. In this research, the content validity of the instrument was established using Lashe's method (Lashe, 1975) and the content validity index (CVI) was found to be 0.77.

Data Analysis

The researchers used descriptive statistics, simple percentages, to analyze the data.

Result and findings

I. To answer the first research question, what are the objectives of the Social Science Pedagogy subject set by Karnataka University?

- (i) The researcher has studied the B.Ed. Syllabus (2015) of Karnataka University. To enrich their knowledge about the subject of Pedagogy, to understand the nature, structure and interrelationships of various components of Social Science,
- (ii) To get acquainted with the latest methods and technologies of teaching Social Science.
- (iii) To get acquainted with the latest methods and technologies of teaching Social Science.
- (iv) To understand the need and importance of teaching Social Science at the secondary level.
- (v) To understand and adopt various methods and assessment techniques.

(vi) It is important to prepare and use various types of teaching materials for teaching Social Science.

II. To answer the second research question;

(i) To what extent are the objectives of social science teaching fulfilled by the curriculum set by Karnataka University?

(ii) The researchers used the 'Pedagogy and Curriculum Evaluation Methodology',

(iii) Seven questions were asked to the student-teachers and teacher educators related to the objectives of teaching social science pedagogy set by the university.

They are shown as follows: -

(i) Does the teaching of Social Science enrich the student teachers' knowledge of the subject?

(ii) Do you think that the current Social Science curriculum is able to contextualize the concerns and needs of society through its structure and components?

(iii) Is it possible to understand the interrelationship of the various components of Social Science through this pedagogy?

(iv) Does this pedagogy evaluate the latest methods and technologies to understand the need and importance of teaching Social Science at the secondary level?

(v) Does this Social Science pedagogy comprehend and adopt various methods and assessment techniques?

(vi) Is the Social Science pedagogy able to justify the need and importance of teaching Social Science at the secondary level?

(vii) Give your opinion on how suitable the Social Science pedagogy is for developing teaching competence in student teachers to teach at the secondary level? Choose any one of the following statements (a) Yes (b) No (c) Can't say (d) Don't know.

Based on the responses given by the student teachers and teacher educators, factor-wise tables were created and analyzed. Accordingly, the following results were found.

Table 2

Note: Student teacher responses (showing the number (N) and percentage (%) of student teachers who chose options a, b, c and d based on the question asked)

Response	a		b		c		d	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
i	28	45%	6	10%	6	10%	0	0%
Ii	23	36%	10	17%	7	12%	0	0%
iii	28	45%	3	5%	5	8%	4	7%
Iv	23	36%	4	7%	10	17%	3	5%
V	28	45%	4	7%	6	10%	2	3%
Vi	34	57%	1	2%	4	7%	1	2%

Figure 2: Factor-wise comparison of student-teacher responses (in %)

Table 3

Teacher Responses

Note: (The item-wise number (N) and percentage (%) of teachers who chose options a, b, c and d based on the question asked are shown)

Response	a		b		d		e	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
i	12	18%	7	12%	1	2%	0	0%
ii	13	20%	1	2%	3	5%	3%	5%
Iii	18	28%	1	2%	1	2%	0	0%
iv	11	18%	2	2%	4	7%	3	5%
v	11	18%	2	3%	4	7%	3	5%
vi	18	28%	1	2%	0%	0%	1	2%

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Figure 3
Item comparison of teacher responses (in %).

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- 45% of student teachers and 18% of teacher teachers indicate that teaching of social science subject enriches the knowledge of student teachers about the subject.
- 36% of student teachers and 20% of teacher teachers conclude that the current social science curriculum is able to contextualize the emerging concerns of Indian society through its structure and components.
- 45% of student teachers and 28% of teacher teachers agree that it is possible to understand the interrelationship of various components of social science through this subject.
- 36% of student teachers and 18% of teacher teachers conclude that this curriculum evaluates the latest methods and technologies to understand the need and importance of teaching social science at the secondary level.
- 45% of student teachers and 18% of teacher teachers agree that this curriculum comprehends and adopts various methods and techniques of assessments.
- It concludes that 57% of student teachers and 28% of teacher educators agree that the social science curriculum justifies the need and importance of teaching social science at the secondary level.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that there is a huge difference between the perceptions of student teachers and teacher educators in all aspects but most of the respondents agree that the objectives of teaching Social Science are fulfilled by the curriculum prescribed by Karnataka University. Similarly, the respondents felt that the teaching of Social Science subject does not enrich the knowledge of the student teachers about the subject and the current Social Science curriculum, through its structure and components, is not able to contextualize the emerging concerns and needs of the Indian society. The subject does not understand the interrelationship of the various components of Social Science and there is no such element to relate other components to each other. The curriculum does not evaluate the latest methods and technologies to understand the need and importance of teaching Social Science at the secondary level but provides some of the most widely used techniques. Overall, the basic knowledge of Social Science subject and the qualities that should be possessed by Social Science teachers are introduced but the latest techniques and methods are not discussed and the old tradition is not incorporated in it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Karnataka University has brought changes in the B.Ed. subject, in the light of the new norms and standards of NCTE, 2014. However, significant content has not been included in the study of Social Science teaching courses. Even after the revision and restructuring of the subject, this is a very unsatisfactory situation for teacher education. Therefore, there is an urgent need to modify the teaching of Social Science subject and fulfill the requirement prescribed in the subject objectives.

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